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Effects of bidding on the success of construction project

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ABSTRACT

Construction bidding is the procedure of submitting a tender (proposal) to undertake or manage the undertaking of a construction project. From project management perspective, it is very important component for proper project performance. Success of any construction project is mainly based on the following three factors: Schedule, Quality and Cost. Bidding process is the project early-stage success evaluating factor which has direct impact on cost and indirect impact schedule and quality of construction project. Bidding process needs a lot of attention not only by contractors to secure the construction project but also by clients for the success of construction project. The research is basically divided into two parts first is to investigate the factor causing flaws in bidding process for successful bid and second is to investigate the effects of wrong bid on construction projects. The result shows that proper management and estimation is very important factor in evaluating the successful bid.

KEYWORDS: Project bidding process, successful construction project, project performance

1 INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is considered as one of the developing countries of world. Construction sector is one of the most important sectors which is striving to get Pakistan out of this label. The construction industry influences the GDP rate and jobs in almost all countries and thus due to this construction sector is considered very important for a country's economic progress. Moreover, Pakistani construction industry just not performs the above listed functions for the betterment but also makes its crucial contribution in the economic industries like Power and energy, Development of water resources and dam technology, Planning and architecture, Engineering in Public Health, communication, Gas, oil and petrochemical. Almost 40-50 other businesses and sectors in the country are directly and indirectly influenced by the accomplishments of construction sector [1] In any project under any constructing firm has almost the same steps of completion. Bidding is the very initial step in the development phase of the project life cycle that decides the progress of the business. Therefore, this phase is therefore an initial important step. [2] Hence Bidding serves as the foundation of construction project life cycle if anything goes wrong with it, that will surely affect the contracting firm and the construction industry as a whole. It is therefore Effective

construction expenses control and cost computation during the bidding phase of customers building projects is of considerable importance.

2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

In addition, with highlighting the importance bidding system in Pakistan, there are mainly three objectives of our research. first one is to find the flaws in our bidding system, second one is to find the factors on which our bidding system relies and third one is to guess the improvement afterword's. this research has given us the basic factors which must be taken in consideration while undergoing the bidding process.

Major factors that will be involved in bidding process will be identified through review of related literature, discussion with practitioners and from the data collected through survey forms filled by different clients, consultant as well as contractors. Final report and bid cost of different construction project will be collected and analysed to evaluate the effect of bidding process on construction project.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

When a construction project is finished in time and within a decided budget and all the stakeholders are satisfied and happy with the performance of contractor, Then the building project is seen as successful [1]. It must also be remembered that Completing construction contracts within the specified time is a used as a measure of performance and efficiency of the contractor or the contracting firm [2]. Hence to make any construction project successful economy and resources estimation is very crucial which is done in the bidding process of the project, so any wrong bid will cause damage to just not only the project but the contracting firm and hence as whole it will affect the construction sector to some extent.

The completion of a construction project on schedule is very rare [3-6]. In many countries, though, the building industry especially, the contracting firms are criticized for the inefficiencies due to outcomes like time and expense overruns, low profitability, bad quality and consumer dissatisfaction [7, 8]. Cost overrun in construction projects is a global problem and the these cost overruns usually results in conflict between owners, project managers and contractors [9, 10].

Cost overruns due to wrong bids is one of the biggest challenges faced by the contracting firms in both developed and developing countries that trigger delays in building industry. [11]. Flyvbjerg [12] analysis found that 9 out of 10 projects in a survey of 258 organizations in 20 countries and five continents worldwide had the problem of cost overruns. In reality, almost every building project takes delays and the severity of such delays varies considerably across projects and countries [13]

According to A. Bagies and C. Fortune inaccurate bid details and cost estimation is considered to be one of the main problems being faced by the contractors [14] The client takes a huge risks by choosing a bid unrealistic low estimate which may be submitted by mistake or unintentionally. [15] and by doing so he just only take a risk of damaging the reputation of his own firm but also the wellbeing of construction industry. Hence, it is essential to recognize the factors that cause overruns in costs to prevent and mitigate problems Because normally the first step in resolving an

issue is to identify the root causes and then after that remedial step can be taken. Since the perennial dilemma of building costs overruns is not sorted out yet so there is still a need of debate and further research to reach a conclusion [16]

In this research paper we have developed a relationship between the wrong bids and project failures. Moreover, we will also investigate about the fundamental causes of cost overruns and then their potential effects on the development of project. Because bids are serving as the very first step to the completion of project so any wrong bid will impact the project adversely and damaging the project means damaging the construction industry.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As discussed in methodology, a questionnaire was distributed among contractors, and they were asked to mark the possible factors involved in wrong bids with 5 being the highest involved in causing wrong bids and 1 being the least. In the presented study different factors causing wrong bids and effects of wrong bids are analysed through statistical analysis technique and results are shown below

4.1 Factors involved in wrong bids

In Table 1 average score of different factors is shown with 5 being the highest and 1 being the lowest. It has clearly been concluded that “**Wrong Estimation of Bill of quantities (BOQ)**” with average score of 4.37 is found out to be the highest factor that results in wrong bid of most of the projects. Moreover “**Competition between Contractors for getting bid**” with average score of 1.37 is the lowest contributing factor for wrong bids by the contractors.

Table 1 Scale of different factors causing wrong bids

FACTORS	Scale
Political Monopoly	3.87
Improper Feasibility Report	4
Rushed Bids/inaccurate takeoffs	3.37
less Experience of firm in related engineering project	1.87
Wrong Estimation of Bill of quantities (BOQ)	4.37
Competition between Contractors for getting bid	1.37
Lack of information flow between parties	3.25
Incomplete design at the time of tender	2.87
fluctuation of prices of materials	2.37

After the Statistical excel analysis of survey data, all scores of factors are summed up as total and then the percent of different factors is calculated. As shown below it can be concluded that 17% of wrong bids occur due to “**Wrong Estimation of Bill of quantities (BOQ)**”. Similarly, from the Graphical presentation it can also be concluded that 5% of the wrong bids are caused due to

“Competition between Contractors for getting bid”. Moreover, from the presented pie chart it can also predicted that how many wrong bids are caused by other factors

Figure 1: Graphical representation of Factors involved in wrong bids

4.2 Effects of wrong bids

In Table 2 average score of different effects that are caused by wrong bids are shown. It has clearly been concluded that “**Poor quality of work**” with average score of 4.75 is found out to be the most abundant effect that is caused by the wrong bids hence it can be said that the quality of work is highly dependent on Bidding if projects and wrong bid will highly be affected in negative manner. Moreover “**Economic un stability of client**” with average score of 1.5 is the least effect that is caused by wrong bids according to different contractors.

Table 2 Scale of different Effects of wrong bids

EFFECTS	SCALE
Delays in project	4.12
Poor quality of work	4.75
Economic un stability of client	1.5
Creates stress to the client	3.87
Total project abandonment	2.12
Bad reputation with client	3.37
Loss of profit to contractor	3.62
Lack of Risk Management	4.37
Litigation	2.25

Below is the graphical representation of percentage of effects resulted in due to wrong bids. After the Statistical excel analysis of the survey data, all scores of effects are summed up as total and then the percent of different effects is calculated.

As shown below it can be concluded that 16% of wrong bids effects “quality of work”. Hence Poor quality of work is the highest effected parameter due to wrong bids. Similarly, from the Graphical presentation it can also be concluded that “Economic un stability of client” with 5% effected rate is being the least paramant effected by wrong bids. Moreover, From the given chart it can also be concluded that wrong bids effect the schedule of projects and causes delays. In addition to that, from the presented pie chart, we can also predict how wrong bids effects other parameters

Figure 2: Graphical representation of Effects of wrong bids

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

Construction companies must be able to handle a variety of bidding scenarios in today's highly competitive market. The first decision they had to make was whether or not to submit a bid after receiving a tender invitation. Several elements and factors have a role in the final decision of the contractors. This selection relies heavily on the specific project and the overall macro environment. Recognition that only the lowest bidder will provide an adequate service has resulted in an increasing desire to transition from "lowest-price wins" to "multi-criteria selection" in the selection process for contractors. hence, the construction industry's competitive bidding process and bid strategy need to be studied.

6 CONCLUSION

Statistical analysis of data collected by questionnaire survey reveals that different factors are involved in bidding process for success of construction projects. Consultants should check the project site and made an estimate according to market prices and then tender the project.

Consultants should not give projects to bids which are lower than their own estimated costs. On the other hand, Contractors should also be regulated under proper authority, so their past performance record is always in front of consultants.

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